

The Relationship Between Risk Acceptance and Project Performance: Evidence from Kenya's Tea Automation Initiative

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Abstract

The implementation of tea system automation projects in Kenya has faced persistent challenges, including delays, cost escalations, technical shortcomings, and insufficient risk management. Among these, inadequate risk acceptance has emerged as a significant contributor to underperformance. This study investigates how risk acceptance influences project outcomes, focusing on 69 tea processing firms under the management of the Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA). Data were gathered from project managers, coordinators, and committee executives, and analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression techniques at a 5% significance level. The results indicate a strong and statistically significant positive correlation between risk acceptance and project performance. The study finds that organizations that proactively acknowledge and manage acceptable risks—rather than avoiding or shifting them—benefit from improved adaptability, more efficient resource use, and enhanced resilience. These factors collectively lead to better project results. The research highlights the importance of integrating risk acceptance into strategic project management to ensure the effective execution and long-term viability of automation initiatives in the tea sector.

Keywords: *tea system automation project, risk acceptance, performance, results, project management.*

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Introduction

Globally, risk acceptance has emerged as a critical strategy in project risk management, especially as organizations navigate increasingly complex and dynamic environments. Risk acceptance involves acknowledging the presence of certain risks and choosing to proceed with the project while preparing to manage the outcomes should those risks materialize. In the United States, while manufacturing firms heavily focus on risk avoidance to manage regulatory and safety concerns, they also recognize the necessity of risk acceptance where innovation and market dynamics demand tolerance for uncertainty (Kerzner, 2017). Similarly, Chinese companies integrate risk acceptance with other strategies to effectively manage vulnerabilities and optimize project outcomes in a highly

competitive environment (Zhang et al., 2019). In Japan, despite a strong cultural emphasis on risk avoidance, firms acknowledge that accepting some level of risk is essential for fostering innovation, efficiency, and global competitiveness (Fukuda, 2015). Across these global examples, risk acceptance is understood as an enabler of resilience and adaptability, crucial for sustaining project performance in volatile markets.

Within the African context, risk acceptance plays a growing role as firms undertake automation and technological projects in an effort to remain competitive. South African firms, particularly in the ICT sector, recognize that technological innovation inherently carries risk and, therefore, willingly accept certain uncertainties associated with automation projects (Phiri & Perng, 2019). By adopting calculated risk acceptance strategies, they are able to leverage the benefits of new technologies while preparing contingency plans for potential setbacks (Nkosi & Lahlang, 2019). In contrast, North African firms tend to focus more on risk avoidance; however, some are beginning to balance their approaches by accepting manageable risks to drive innovation and growth (Kaisa & Thekiso, 2018). Overall, the regional trend suggests a gradual shift toward embracing risk acceptance as firms realize that avoiding all risks can stifle technological advancement and competitive advantage.

In Kenya, firms involved in automation projects are increasingly recognizing the importance of integrating risk acceptance into their risk management practices. While traditional approaches heavily emphasized risk avoidance and transference, recent studies indicate that firms are now more open to accepting certain risks as a way of fostering innovation and enhancing project performance (Okaka & Nyabuti, 2019; Waiganjo & Mayaka, 2018). Kenyan software development professionals, for instance, acknowledge that not all risks can be eliminated, and therefore acceptance combined with robust mitigation strategies is essential to project success (Kinyua, 2015). Moreover, in sectors like tea development and construction, stakeholders are beginning to appreciate that calculated risk acceptance allows for flexibility in project execution, enabling firms to capitalize on emerging opportunities without being paralyzed by fear of potential setbacks (Kirui, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

According to the Kenya Tea Development Agency (2022), increased automation in the tea sector over the last decade has led firms to install robust IT platforms such as System Applications and Processes (SAP), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems, Electronic Weighment Systems (EWS), Electronic Document Management Systems (EDMS), and Automated Fleet Management Systems (AFMS) to improve efficiency. Despite these efforts, the cost of production in Kenya remains among the highest globally, threatening the country's competitiveness (World Bank, 2023; RoK, 2023). Poor performance of system automation projects within KTDA firms has been partly attributed to ineffective project risk management strategies (KTDA, 2023). Specifically, the acceptance of certain unavoidable risks, such as uncertainties in global tea prices and technological complexities, has been critical yet inadequately managed. By failing to strategically embrace risk acceptance acknowledging and preparing for the inevitable risks rather than trying to eliminate all uncertainties many KTDA automation projects have struggled to achieve cost reductions and competitiveness gains. Previous studies have often overlooked the unique role of risk acceptance in automation projects, focusing mainly on project implementation or risk prevention (Moler, 2022; De Juan & Hänze, 2021).

Furthermore, limited research has examined risk acceptance within manufacturing and tea processing contexts (Moywaywa, 2018; Mwamba et al., 2019). As existing studies largely adopt quantitative methods (Zhu, 2022), there is a growing need for qualitative investigations that can provide deeper insights into how risk acceptance impacts the success of system automation projects in Kenyan tea processing firms. Understanding and improving risk acceptance strategies would

enable government, communities, policymakers, and business leaders to design more effective interventions, ensuring better performance and sustainability of tea sector automation initiatives.

Objective of the Study

The study's overall objective was to assess the impact of project risk acceptance on tea automation project performance in Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis framed the study:

H₀₁: Project risk acceptance has no statistical effect on performance of tea system automation project in Kenya.

Literature Review

Uncertainty theory, also known as Knightian uncertainty, was formulated by economist Frank Knight in the year 1921. Knight introduced the concept in his book "Risk, Uncertainty, and Profit," where he distinguished between risk, which can be quantified and measured probabilistically, and uncertainty, which cannot. Knightian uncertainty refers to situations where the probabilities of outcomes are unknown or unknowable, making decision-making more difficult and requiring different approaches than those used for risk management (Msinanga & Jiyane, 2017). Uncertainty risk influences how project management should approach stakeholder management. Identification of prospective risks that could jeopardize the project, planning of preventative measures to reduce negative outcomes, and the various contingent courses of action that are then triggered by the events are all required for dealing with expected risks (Mayende & Shumba, 2019). Even with safeguards, certain threats cannot be totally avoided. As a result, project managers must be prepared for unforeseen events and establish measures to mitigate the harm that risks may cause. The theory hence relates to the objective on risk acceptance in project management (Phiri & Perng, 2019).

Projects are inherently subject to various forms of uncertainty, not merely due to task complexity or the nature of interrelationships. A widely accepted approach is to categorise uncertainties based on their origin—such as technical challenges, market conditions, human factors, cost, schedule, or quality—or by their potential impact (Hazir & Ulusoy, 2020; Sikudi, 2018). Effectively managing uncertainty is considered essential for successful project execution. The sources of uncertainty are diverse and can significantly influence both project outcomes and management processes (Chirumbolo & Urbini, 2021; Atkinson, Crawford, & Ward, 2006). These sources extend beyond unpredictable events and encompass factors such as incomplete information, ambiguity, the characteristics of project stakeholders, the balance between trust and control, and differing objectives across the various phases of the project lifecycle (Asplund & Eliasson, 2016; Atkinson, Crawford, & Ward, 2006).

The critics of Uncertainty Theory may lead to overly cautious decision-making or paralysis in the face of uncertainty. Projects often require action despite incomplete information, and an excessive focus on uncertainty may hinder progress or innovation (Waiganjo & Mayaka, 2018). Uncertainty Theory may struggle to provide actionable guidance for managing uncertainties effectively. It may lack specific methodologies or tools for quantifying, prioritizing, and addressing uncertainties, making it challenging to translate theoretical insights into practical risk management practices (Otieno & Kiemo, 2019). Uncertainty Theory may struggle to provide guidance on how to effectively communicate and engage stakeholders in the context of projects. It may overlook the complexities of interpersonal dynamics, power relationships, and cultural differences that influence communication effectiveness and stakeholder interactions (Okaka & Nyabuti, 2019). By integrating

Uncertainty Theory into the risk management strategies and performance evaluation of tea development system automation projects in Kenya provides a more nuanced and adaptive approach to dealing with unpredictability and ambiguity. The Uncertainty theory will be used in this study to assess the effect of risk acceptance on performance of system automation project in Kenya Tea Development Agency firms.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study sought to demonstrate the relationship between project risk acceptance and performance of the tea system automation project in Kenya (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
Source: Busiliru, Paul, & Lango, (2024)

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive research design to examine the relationship between project risk transference strategies and the performance of the tea development system automation project in Kenya. As reported by the Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA), it currently manages 69 active tea processing firms. These firms constituted the unit of analysis. The unit of observation, or target population, comprised 345 individuals, including 69 project managers, 69 project coordinators, and 207 committee executives. To determine an appropriate sample size, the study utilised Slovin’s formula, given the relatively large number of units in the population—namely employees and board members (Zimmermann, 2023). The researcher adopted a 95% confidence level, corresponding to a standard normal deviate of 1.96, and an allowable margin of error of 5% (0.05). The following formula was applied to calculate the sample size for this large population:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2} \quad (1)$$

Where: n = Sample size,

N = Total population and

e = Error tolerance (confidence level).

Since the population N = 345,

Error tolerance = 0.05,

The sample size was determined as: n=185.

Results

Respondents were asked to indicate their level of agreement with a series of statements related to various aspects of risk acceptance. Risk acceptance was conceptualised as a unidimensional construct, assessed using seven specific indicators: the allocation of resources by the firm to address potential risks (RAC1); analysis of the costs associated with possible risks (RAC2); instances where the company deliberately takes no action on risks, even when those risks could affect the project (RAC3); promotion of alternative plans to mitigate project delays (RAC4); the project manager's knowledge of the risk analysis process (RAC5); regular updates provided to management on anticipated risks and risk retention strategies (RAC6); and the use of appropriate technologies to support the acceptance and retention of risks (RAC7).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for the Construct Risk Acceptance

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean	Std. Dev
RAC1	0.9	2.1	12.8	21.3	59.9	4.498	.321
RAC2	7.4	0.8	11.8	22.1	57.9	4.355	.387
RAC3	2.0	3.8	5.3	24.5	64.4	4.213	.486
RAC4	5.4	4.5	9.1	18.2	62.8	4.465	.172
RAC5	5.8	2.1	8.9	17.4	65.8	4.278	.903
RAC6	7.4	0.8	11.8	22.1	57.9	4.355	.387
RAC7	2.0	3.8	5.3	24.5	64.4	4.213	.486
Composite						4.355	.414

The results are as shown in Table 1. According to the findings, the respondents agreed that the firm has allocated resources for any risk that may occur ($M=4.498$, $SD=0.321$). The respondents agreed that the costs of possible risks are analyzed ($M=4.355$, $SD=0.387$). The respondents agreed that the company occasionally does nothing about risks despite the fact that identified risks could have an impact on the project, ($M=4.213$, $SD=0.486$). The respondents also agreed that the company promotes the use of alternate plans to prevent any situations that cause project delays ($M=4.465$, $SD=0.172$). In addition, the respondents agreed that the project manager has enough knowledge on risk analysis process ($M=4.278$, $SD=0.903$). The respondents also agreed that the management is continuously updated on the anticipated risks and retention tactics ($M=4.465$, $SD=0.172$). Lastly, the respondents agreed that the utilizing the right technologies facilitates accepting and retaining risks ($M=4.355$, $SD=0.387$).

The high agreement on resource allocation and promotion of alternate plans indicates a proactive approach to risk management within the organization. While the analysis of risk costs is generally agreed upon, there might be some variation in how extensively this analysis is conducted. The occasional inaction on identified risks suggests potential areas for improvement in risk response strategies. The variability in perceptions regarding the project manager's knowledge on risk analysis highlights the importance of ensuring consistent understanding and competency among project management personnel. Continuous updates on risks and the utilization of appropriate technologies are perceived positively, indicating a commitment to staying informed and leveraging tools for effective risk management. The study findings imply that risk acceptance affect performance of system automation project. A study on risk acceptance and its impact on the performance of tea development system automation projects in Kenya Tea Development Agency (KTDA)-managed firms would have several implications: Investigating risk acceptance sheds light on the risk management strategies employed by KTDA-managed firms. It highlights the extent to which firms are willing to tolerate or embrace certain risks in pursuit of project objectives, as

opposed to avoiding or mitigating them. Understanding risk acceptance behaviors informs the development of tailored risk management approaches that align with organizational risk tolerance levels.

The study illuminates the relationship between risk acceptance and project performance in tea development system automation projects. It assesses whether embracing certain risks leads to better project outcomes, such as improved efficiency, cost-effectiveness, innovation, and stakeholder satisfaction. Analyzing performance outcomes helps identify the impact of risk acceptance on project success and informs strategies for optimizing risk acceptance decisions necessitate transparent communication and stakeholder engagement within KTDA-managed firms. Open dialogue about project risks, risk management strategies, and the rationale behind risk acceptance decisions fosters stakeholder buy-in and support. Effective communication builds trust, enhances collaboration, and mitigates potential conflicts arising from differing risk perceptions. Comparative analysis of risk acceptance practices across KTDA-managed firms and industry benchmarks informs best practices in risk management. Identifying successful risk acceptance strategies and lessons learned from peers helps improve risk management capabilities, mitigate common pitfalls, and enhance project performance across the tea industry. Overall, a study on risk acceptance and its implications for the performance of tea development system automation projects in KTDA-managed firms provides valuable insights for optimizing risk management practices, enhancing project outcomes, and promoting organizational resilience in a dynamic and uncertain environment.

Hypothesis Testing

The regression results show a moderate positive relationship between Project Risk acceptance and Project Performance, with a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.654. The R-Square value of 0.428 indicates that 42.8% of the variance in Project Performance is explained by Project Risk acceptance. After adjusting for the number of predictors, the Adjusted R-Square is 0.398, meaning that 39.8% of the variance in Project Performance can still be attributed to Project Risk acceptance. The standard error of the estimate (0.54876) reflects a moderate level of prediction error, suggesting that while the model offers a reasonably good fit, there are other variables influencing performance that are not captured by Risk Acceptance alone. These findings imply that Project Risk Acceptance plays a substantial role in enhancing project outcomes, but it is not the sole determinant of performance. This aligns with previous studies, such as those by Chapman and Ward (2011), which emphasize that effective risk management, particularly risk avoidance, contributes positively to project success but must be integrated with other risk management strategies for optimal results (Waller, 2015). Moreover, research by PMI (2021) reinforces the idea that while risk avoidance improves project predictability and outcomes, a comprehensive approach addressing multiple risks and management dimensions is essential for ensuring overall project success. Thus, while project risk acceptance is important, broader risk management practices and performance factors should be considered for better project results.

Table 2. Model Summary for Project Risk Acceptance

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.654	.428	.398	.54876

A significant effect of Project Risk Acceptance on project performance is evident from the ANOVA results in Table 3. The regression sum of squares (585.459) and a high F-statistic of 115.909, with a p-value of 0.000, confirm that the model is statistically significant. This indicates

that Project Risk Acceptance explains a substantial portion of the variance in Project Performance. The low residual sum of squares (782.438) and mean square of 5.047 suggest that the unexplained variation in performance is relatively low compared to the influence of Project Risk Acceptance. The findings imply that adopting project risk acceptance strategies positively influences the success of projects, as it significantly contributes to performance improvement. This is consistent with existing literature, such as works by Hillson (2009) and PMI (2021), which argue that when risks are well-understood and accepted, projects can be better managed, leading to enhanced performance outcomes. The implication is that organizations should consider risk acceptance as a critical part of their risk management framework to drive better project results.

Table 3. ANOVA Statistics (Project Risk Acceptance against Project Performance)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	585.459	1	585.459	115.909	.000
Residual	782.438	155	5.047		
Total	1367.897	156			

Table 4 presents the regression coefficients for the independent variable (project risk acceptance) and the dependent variable (performance of the tea development automation system project). The results indicate that when project risk acceptance is held constant, the baseline project performance index is 7.987. Furthermore, the Beta coefficient for the relationship between project risk acceptance and project performance is 0.698, suggesting that a one-unit increase in project risk acceptance leads to a 0.698-unit increase in project performance. The t-value of 3.455 exceeds the critical threshold of ± 1.96 , indicating that the observed effect is statistically significant and unlikely to have occurred by chance. The p-value of 0.000 is below the 0.05 significance level, confirming the reliability of the relationship. Based on these results, the regression equation is expressed as $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$, where X_1 represents project risk acceptance and Y represents project performance. Substituting the values, the model becomes: Project Performance = 7.987 + 0.698 * Project Risk Acceptance.

Therefore, the analysis concludes that project risk acceptance has a positive and statistically significant influence on the performance of the tea development automation system project in Kenya. The results further validate this conclusion, as shown in Table 4, with a significant relationship established ($\beta_1 = 0.698$, $t_{cal} = 5.768 > t_{critical} = 1.96$, $p < 0.05$). Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{01}): Project risk acceptance has no significant relationship with project performance in Kenya, is rejected. It is thus affirmed that project risk acceptance (X_1) significantly and positively impacts the performance of the tea development automation system project (Y).

Table 4. Regression Coefficients (Project Risk Acceptance and Project Performance)

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	7.987	1.324		6.032	.000
Project Risk Acceptance	.698	.121	.654	5.768	.000

Discussion

The results of the regression analysis show a moderate positive relationship between Project Risk Acceptance and Project Performance. It suggests that while risk acceptance is a substantial predictor of performance, other factors also contribute significantly to project outcomes. Even after adjusting for possible complexity in the model, the relationship remains strong and reliable. Although there is some prediction error, Project Risk Acceptance still stands out as a meaningful influence on project success. The significance of the relationship is further confirmed by statistical tests, reinforcing that accepting and managing known risks, rather than attempting to eliminate all risks, enhances project outcomes. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which emphasize that embracing manageable risks leads to more predictable and successful project results.

Furthermore, the analysis reveals that Project Risk Acceptance significantly and positively impacts project performance. An improvement in risk acceptance practices is associated with notable improvements in project outcomes. The strong significance of the results rejects the notion that risk acceptance has no impact, confirming its critical role in enhancing project performance. This implies that Kenyan tea processing firms should place greater emphasis on identifying, understanding, and accepting certain risks, rather than focusing solely on risk avoidance. By doing so, they can improve efficiency, better control costs, and strengthen their competitiveness. Overall, the results highlight that strategic risk acceptance should be a central part of project management frameworks to achieve successful automation initiatives in the tea sector.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study confirms that project risk acceptance positively and significantly influences the performance of tea development automation projects in Kenya. Therefore, embracing risk acceptance as part of a broader risk management strategy is crucial for enhancing project success and maintaining competitiveness in the sector. It is recommended that tea processing firms in Kenya, particularly those under KTDA, strengthen their project risk management frameworks by actively incorporating risk acceptance strategies. By fostering a culture that identifies, assesses, and deliberately accepts manageable risks, firms can enhance project outcomes, drive automation success, and improve overall competitiveness in the global market.

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